

DIGITAL INTERACTIVE SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL IN BIOTECHNOLOGY FOR GRADE 8 LEARNERS

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Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology for Grade 8 Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to develop a digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology for Grade 8 learners. It aimed to help the learners in coping with the lessons and improve their performance in selected lessons in Biotechnology. Twenty-seven (27) learners from Grade 8 Special Science Class of Angono National High School in the School Year 2023-2024 were purposively selected as respondents of the study. The Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology was developed based on the competencies in Biotechnology during the third quarter. It sought to determine the level of performance and the significant difference in the level of performance of the learners before and after exposure to the developed supplementary material. The mean and standard deviation were utilized to determine the level of performance of the students as revealed in their pretest and posttest results. Additionally, dependent t-test was used to determine the significant difference in the level of performance of the students. The research method used was quasi-experimental design to determine the level of performance of learners in the pretest and posttest results and the difference between the pretest and posttest scores before and after the exposure to the developed material. The validity of the digital interactive material was validated by master teachers and experts Science instructors and professors. The data gathered before and after exposure to the developed material revealed from "Average" to "High" verbal interpretations in which the developed digital interactive supplementary material was utilized with respect to the different competencies which showed an improved performance of the learners after the exposure to the developed material. The result of the t-test revealed that there was a significant difference between the performance of the Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology. The researcher concluded that the level of performance of the Grade 8 learners had a significant difference before and after utilizing the developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology. Hence, the supplementary material improved the level of performance of the learners in all the competencies in which the developed material was used.

Keywords: *digital, biotechnology, learners, material*

Introduction

The rise of digitalization in schools across the world means that traditional teaching methods are changing, and technologies are taking over classrooms. Learners now have instant access to resources in any location because of the digital revolution in education. The education industry is by no means left behind in the contemporary digital environment, where technology takes center stage.

In the country, the educational landscape is continuously adapting and responding in the various alterations in the system, specifically in the delivery of learning to ensure that education serves its purposes, including the acquisition of knowledge as well as the investigation of human empowerment and growth for one's own future well-being, whether socially or economically. (Calindog, 2022)

DepEd Order No. 21, series of 2019, entitled Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program, states that:

“The curriculum is articulated in terms of standards and competencies and is seamless, research-based and decongested. It uses the spiral progression approach to ensure mastery of knowledge and skills after each level. Information and Communications Technology (ICT) competencies have been integrated into the curriculum to equip learners with skills that will enable them to cope with the technological demands of our time.”

The order clearly stated that the use of ICT, such as digitalization of supplementary material, that will support technological capabilities are essential. The inclusion of technology for lesson delivery in classrooms is progressively becoming the new normal nationally. While there may be initial costs associated with acquiring ICT tools and resources, in the long run, digital content and online resources can be more cost-effective than traditional textbooks and materials. Additionally, ICT can save time for teachers by automating tasks such as grading.

Martin et al. (2020) stated that as learners and teachers return to in-person learning, the educational technology sector is unlikely to relinquish their profits or decrease their product offerings. They further added that some schools will continue to use fully online learning, but many more will use forms of blended learning where instruction can be provided through both traditional and online modalities in ratios that meet the needs of the learners and match the resources in the school.

In this course of digitalization, schools are somehow forced to transform analog, location-based teaching methods into digital, location-independent learning opportunities. Teachers are now challenged to initiate and accompany more in the classroom. Furthermore, trends in technology and digitalization are within reach at the tip of the fingers. Every learner can play almost any game online, search and learn online, and chat online anytime and anywhere. Not only that, these are all possible and available in one of the smallest

communication gadgets, cellphone. Moreover, one does not need to own one, since everyone may access the internet especially in this era.

Digital interactive learning materials are tools that can be used to teach a certain learning objective. They may consist of a single page or several pages, and any mix of text, photos, audio, and video may be used, including screencasts, animations, questions for a self-test, and other interactive elements. These materials can be made available as extra resources or as a crucial component of a primary activity, such as a requirement to attend a scheduled lecture. Due to the advantages, they are starting to appear frequently in both educational programs and on numerous support service websites.

Furthermore, digital interactive learning requires learner participation in a technological approach. This participation can come through the use of computer, laptop or even a smart phone. However, not all forms of interactivity are equally effective for all learners. This is true even though the broad definition of "interactive" makes developing and instructing such a class relatively simple. For instance, shy learners are probably less likely to gain from conversations in class where involvement is optional. By enabling teachers to create and employ active learning resources, technology has greatly benefited this situation.

Moreso, digital learning broadens learners access to education and knowledge while equipping them with skills and a mentality that will help them succeed now and in the future. Numerous studies indicate that just providing learners with access to devices does not guarantee better results; instead, effective integration and active adoption of a digital mindset are required for digital learning to significantly improve the entire learning experience.

The researcher highlighted the use of digital interactive material that can improve the mastery of the competencies. Thus, the research aimed to develop digital interactive supplementary material to be used in Biotechnology.

The global problem or issue widespread in schools and other educational institution today is underachievement. Underachievement is now a widely used term in education policy and practice. It has been used to denote low achievement in general as well as low achievement when compared to one of these categories and lesser achievement when compared to what an observer might anticipate.

Digital instructional materials that are created to assist learners and teachers in the teaching and learning process often reside in an electronic source or digital library for access. This too can have broad application and include everything from snippets of video to full-year textbooks in a digital format along with all the video, audio, text, animation, simulations, and assessments in between. Thus, digital instructional materials can include smaller "chunks," such as individual chapters or lessons, allowing for flexibility in creation, distribution, and usage (Setda, 2019).

However, there is a noticeable shortage of such materials in Biotechnology particularly in Genetics. Many learners encounter difficulties in comprehending how heredity and genetic disorders happen. This shortage emphasizes the need for researchers and educators to address this problem.

The junior high school of Angono National High School offers Special Science Program with curriculum that offers advanced subjects in Science, Mathematics and ICT. Among all the offered subjects, Biotechnology is identified with low mean percentage score in tests as revealed in the Learning Outcome Assessment (LOA) reports. These reports refer to the evaluation process used to measure learners' attainment of learning outcomes. The researcher believed that by addressing this problem and applying effective teaching strategies together with appropriate instructional materials, learners may develop a profound understanding on the competencies in Biotechnology. The developed digital interactive supplementary material may contribute to the learners and the burden of the teachers in delivering lessons will also be lessened.

Research Questions

The study focused on the development of digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology for Grade 8 learners. Specifically, it sought answers the following questions:

1. What is the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology with respect to the different competencies:
 - 1.1. Explain how the traits are inherited according to Mendel's Law of Heredity;
 - 1.2. Identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance;
 - 1.3. Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number; and
 - 1.4. Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited?
2. Is there a significant difference on the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology with respect to the cited competencies?

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher used the quasi-experimental research design as approach in gathering data on the developed Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology for Grade 8 Learners.

According to Thomas (2020), a quasi-experimental design aims to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable. However, unlike a true experiment, a quasi-experiment does not rely on random assignment. Instead, subjects are assigned to groups based on non-random criteria. This design is a useful tool in situations where true experiments cannot be used for ethical or practical reasons. Damyanov (2023) also added that a quasi-experimental is a research design in which the independent variable is manipulated, but participants are not randomly assigned to conditions.

The researcher preferred to use this design because it is not logistically feasible to conduct randomized testing in Grade 8 special science class but also because this design was substantial in the developing of the material as it allowed the researcher to manipulate variables to help her meet the objectives of the study.

Respondents

The study involved a total enumeration of twenty-seven (27) Grade 8 learners enrolled in the Special Science Class at Angono National High School as the respondents. Their acceptance into the program was contingent upon their desire to take a specialized scientific course. The researcher carefully selected these respondents using purposeful sampling techniques.

Likewise, the developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology were validated by master teachers of Science in the Angono National High School and instructors and professors in the University of Rizal System – Morong Campus. These experts were purposively selected based on the subjects they have handled and expertise in the field of science and research.

Instrument

An exam that the researcher devised herself, centered on the competencies covered in the third quarter of the biotechnology course, served as the primary instrument for collecting the necessary data.

Strict validation processes were carried out by the science experts on the researcher's test, which included an analysis of its face validity and content validity. The test consisted of forty (40) multiple-choice questions divided into several competencies, with 10 questions per competency.

The researcher meticulously matched the test items to the specification table. The specification table, which included information on the subjects taught, lesson lengths, item numbers, and item distribution, guaranteed a comprehensive evaluation of learners' comprehension. For the first eighty (80) multiple-choice questions, the researcher ran an item analysis. The Grade 9 Special Science Class learners from Angono National High School, who had finished the biotechnology course, participated in this study.

The researcher refined the exam questions after the item analysis, yielding a selection of forty (40) items. The researcher then ran a test-retest reliability analysis on these updated items to provide further assessment. The study administered the revised test items to a new group of learners to ensure the validity and consistency of the assessment instruments used.

Procedure

The researcher used a Gantt Chart in the conduct of the study. It also shows the duration of months covering the research study. This spanned from the formulation of the research problem to the revision and submission of the final copy of the manuscript.

After the proposal defense, the researcher begun with the revision of the manuscript to secure a permit to conduct the study and proceeded in the development process. The researcher obtained permission from the Schools Division Office of Rizal to conduct the study. The researcher gathered the data from Learning Outcome Assessment (LOA) to analyze the least mastered competencies in the Special Program in Science. The identified least mastered competencies were Mendel's Law of Heredity and Genetic Disorders in Biotechnology.

Subsequently, the researcher proceeded to the development of the digital interactive supplementary material specifically targeting the least mastered competencies in Biotechnology. The developed digital interactive supplementary material was carefully crafted and reviewed by the researcher's adviser to ensure its usefulness and relevance. After the output was developed, it undergone content validation by the selected Science master teachers from Angono National High School and instructors and professors from University of Rizal System - Morong Campus.

The developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology underwent revisions based on feedback received from the experts during the face and content validation. The researcher incorporated all the suggestions and recommendations from the experts to improve the developed material. The development of the researcher-made test involved creating a detailed table of specifications. The test consisted of 40 items and underwent face and content validation, item analysis, and test-retest reliability checks. The material was then exposed and administered to the Grade 8 Special Science Class for assessment purposes.

In determining the level of performance of the learners the researcher conducted tests before and after exposure to the developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology. The data collected from before and after exposure to the developed material were analyzed using statistical methods such as mean and dependent t-tests to evaluate learners' performance.

Finally, the collected data were encoded, processed, analyzed, and interpreted. The summary of findings, conclusions and

recommendations were formulated. After the oral defense, the manuscript was revised considering the comments and suggestions of the Oral Examination Committee. After finalization, hard bound copies were submitted to the office of the Graduate School and other offices.

Data Analysis

For the analysis and interpretation of data, the following statistical tools were considered:

To determine the level of performance of the learners before and after exposure to the developed digital interactive supplementary material, mean and standard deviation were used.

To determine the significant difference on the level of performance of the Grade 8 learners, dependent t-test was used.

Results and Discussion

The Level of Performance of Grade 8 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material with Respect to the Different Competencies

Table 1 shows the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the digital interactive supplementary material with respect to the different competencies.

Table 1. *Level of Performance of Grade 8 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material with Respect to the Different Competencies*

Competencies	Before			After		
	Mean	Sd.	VI	Mean	Sd.	VI
1.1 Explain how the traits are inherited according to Mendel's Law of Heredity.	4.41	1.647	Average	9.30	0.82	High
1.2 Identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance.	4.70	1.514	Average	9.22	0.93	High
1.3 Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number.	4.44	1.649	Average	9.11	1.05	High
1.4 Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited.	4.07	1.639	Average	9.11	1.01	High
Total	17.63	4.829	Average	36.74	1.85	High

As shown on the table, the competency "Explain how the traits are inherited according to Mendel's Law of Heredity" obtained a mean of 4.41 and a standard deviation of 1.647 and verbal interpretation of "Average" before exposure to the developed supplementary material. After exposure to the developed material, the mean score was 9.30 and was interpreted as "High" and the standard deviation decreased to 0.823.

As to the competency "Identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance", the mean score was 4.70 with standard deviation of 1.514 and verbal interpretation of "Average" before exposure to the developed supplementary material. Then, after exposure, the mean score obtained was 9.22 and the standard deviation was 0.934 with verbal interpretation of "High".

Meanwhile, the mean score of 4.4 and standard deviation of 1.649 with verbal interpretation of "Average" was obtained by the competency "Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number" before the exposure to the developed material. The results gained increased after exposure to the material with the mean score of 9.11 and standard deviation of 1.050 and verbal interpretation of "High".

Lastly, in the competency "Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited", the obtained mean before exposure was 4.07 and standard deviation of 1.639 with a verbal interpretation of "Average". After exposure to the developed material, the table showed a mean score of 9.11 and a standard deviation of 1.013 and "High" verbal interpretation.

Moreover, before the exposure of the learners on the developed supplementary material, the obtained total mean was 17.63 with a standard deviation of 4.829 and verbal interpretation of "Average". This could mean that before exposure, learners have only limited knowledge with regards to the given competencies. After exposure to the developed supplementary material, the total mean score was 36.74 with a standard deviation of 1.852 with a verbal interpretation of "High". This significantly emphasizes that the increase in the mean score, having been exposed to the developed supplementary material, shows that the learners gained more knowledge and skills in the given competencies.

The results of the study showed that the Grade 8 Special Science Class learners benefited from the developed Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology. Furthermore, the findings demonstrated that the developed digital interactive supplementary material successfully fulfilled the learning competencies in Biotechnology, specifically in Genetics. Thus, this confirmed that the developed material significantly contributed to enhancing learner performance.

The findings implied that the developed Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology positively linked with the

improved learners’ performance. The result also implied that the learners’ exposure to the developed digital interactive supplementary material contributed to enhancing their critical thinking skills, hence, showing better understanding of the lessons.

This was supported by the study of Malicoban et al. (2021) wherein they stated that supplementary materials support wide range of ideas, concepts, perspectives and quality on the process. The researcher perceived that utilizing the developed supplementary material definitely helps the learners in uplifting the level of understanding into more meaningful way of learning. Furthermore, Mondragon et al. (2023) added that utilizing digital supplementary material provides valuable insights for educators who seek to promote the importance of leveraging technology in support of learning outcomes. Thus, the supplementary material made genuine contribution in the development and betterment of academic performance of the learners to achieve the desired learning outcomes.

The Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of Grade 8 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology with Respect to the Different Competencies

Table 2 on the next page shows the significant difference on the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the digital interactive supplementary material with respect to the different competencies.

As gleaned on the table on the next page, the corresponding p-values of the competencies such as: explain how the traits are inherited according to Mendel’s Law of Heredity, identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance, explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number, and explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited are all .000 which is less than 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference on the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material in Biotechnology with respect to the competencies was rejected.

Table 2. Significant Difference on the Level of Performance of Grade 8 Learners Before and After Exposure to the Digital Interactive Supplementary Material with Respect to the Different Competencies

Competencies		Mean	Sd.	Mean Diff	t	df	Sig.	Ho	VI																																													
1.1 Explain how the traits are inherited according to Mendel’s Law of Heredity.	Before	4.41	1.65	4.889	13.914	26	.000	R	S																																													
	After	9.30	0.82							1.2 Identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance.	Before	4.70	1.51	4.519	16.807	26	.000	R	S	After	9.22	0.93	1.3 Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number.	Before	4.44	1.65	4.667	12.753	26	.000	R	S	After	9.11	1.05	1.4 Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited.	Before	4.07	1.64	5.037	18.001	26	.000	R	S	After	9.11	1.01	Total	Before	17.63	4.83	19.111	20.870
1.2 Identify and explain the different traits that do not follow the Mendelian Pattern of Inheritance.	Before	4.70	1.51	4.519	16.807	26	.000	R	S																																													
	After	9.22	0.93							1.3 Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number.	Before	4.44	1.65	4.667	12.753	26	.000	R	S	After	9.11	1.05	1.4 Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited.	Before	4.07	1.64	5.037	18.001	26	.000	R	S	After	9.11	1.01	Total	Before	17.63	4.83	19.111	20.870	26	.000	R	S	After	36.74	1.85						
1.3 Explain the different genetic disorders brought about by changes in chromosome structure and number.	Before	4.44	1.65	4.667	12.753	26	.000	R	S																																													
	After	9.11	1.05							1.4 Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited.	Before	4.07	1.64	5.037	18.001	26	.000	R	S	After	9.11	1.01	Total	Before	17.63	4.83	19.111	20.870	26	.000	R	S	After	36.74	1.85																			
1.4 Explain how the different autosomal genetic disorders are inherited.	Before	4.07	1.64	5.037	18.001	26	.000	R	S																																													
	After	9.11	1.01							Total	Before	17.63	4.83	19.111	20.870	26	.000	R	S	After	36.74	1.85																																
Total	Before	17.63	4.83	19.111	20.870	26	.000	R	S																																													
	After	36.74	1.85																																																			

The results revealed that the lessons in the competencies with help of the developed supplementary material increased the performance level of the learners. The total mean score after exposure is 36.74 which is greater than the mean before exposure which is 17.63.

Furthermore, it showed that the learners had remarkably enhanced their understanding of the subject matter. This highlighted the importance digital learning in attaining desired learning outcomes and supports the usefulness of the developed digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology.

This implied that the exposure of the learners to the developed supplementary material is an important teaching aid that can be used in teaching and learning process. It suggested that incorporating digital interactive supplementary materials can lead to enhanced attainment of learning. This was also strengthened by the study of San Diego (2015) which denotes that using supplementary materials can help the learners comprehend the lesson and served as a motivating factor in grasping their attention to learn.

Conclusions

Based on the summary of findings, it was found that there is a significant difference on the level of performance of Grade 8 learners before and after exposure to the digital interactive supplementary material in Biotechnology with respect to the competencies. Therefore, the use of the digital interactive supplementary material exhibited contribution in attaining desirable learning outcomes.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following are hereby recommended:

The developed supplementary material may be subjected to a continuous revision and modification to match the learning needs of

learners in the future.

Future researchers may modify the digital interactive supplementary material into a web application for better usage and experience.

Future researchers may conduct a study in testing the effectiveness of the digital interactive supplementary material.

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